

2nd CSIRO Symposium on COMPUTATIONAL CHALLENGES IN LIFE SCIENCES

5-7 February 1996 Melbourne AUSTRALIA

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2ND CSIRO SYMPOSIUM ON "COMPUTATIONAL CHALLENGES IN LIFE SCIENCES"

5-7 FEBRUARY 1996

MELBOURNE

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Symposium WWW home page:

<http://www.mel.dit.csiro.au/LifeSci/cfp.html>

Welcome to the Symposium

On behalf of the Organising and the Program Committees and the CSIRO Supercomputing Support Group we would like to welcome you to this Symposium. A special welcome to those attending from overseas and interstate.

Following the success of the first Symposium in May 1994, the Supercomputing Support Group (SSG) of CSIRO undertook a task to run the Second Symposium. Our aim is to highlight further how computation is being used to extend the boundaries of knowledge in biological sciences. This methodology is maturing very fast and finds application in vastly different fields of research. We had to make choices. We decided to concentrate on the topics which were highlighted in the First Symposium and which are very strongly represented in Australia. The two examples are computational neurosciences and plant simulations. We hope that an excellent program in these two areas will help in strengthening them here in Australia even further and will showcase the continuing growth and promise in these areas.

The location of this conference indicates also strength and potential in molecular biology, biochemistry, drug design and related fields. We are right in the heart of an area of biomedical research: next to the University of Melbourne and Parkville, with world-class research establishments such as the Walter and Eliza Hall Institute, Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research, the CSIRO Division of Biomolecular Engineering, the Biomolecular Research Institute, Victorian College of Pharmacy, and the University's medical school and teaching hospitals.

The CSIRO Supercomputing Facility is based in Melbourne, but provides services to CSIRO Australia-wide. We hope that this will be an Australian event, open to all with interests in computational Life Sciences.

Organisation of an event such as this one requires hard work and cooperation of many individuals. Our special thanks are due to Heather Vile, Sue Wilson and Jim Taylor of the CSIRO Division of Information Technology for their contribution; to the members of the CSIRO Supercomputing Support Group: Len Makin and Virginia Norling for everyday work and help. We are very grateful to the members of the Program Committee, especially to Prof John Furness, Dr Jill Gready and Dr Frances Separovic for advice which was crucial to the success to this meeting.

Lastly, we would like to thank our sponsors for their support, financial and otherwise, without which the Symposium would not have been possible. We thank all those who will be presenting papers, posters and demonstrations at the Symposium for making this an exciting and memorable meeting.

We hope you both enjoy the Symposium and find it stimulating.

Marek Michalewicz and Rob Bell

For the Organising Committee

	MONDAY, 5 Feb '96	TUESDAY, 6 Feb '96	WEDNESDAY, 7 Feb '96
8:30 - 8:50	Registration and Morning Coffee <i>Foyer</i>	Day Registration and Morning Coffee	Day Registration and Morning Coffee
	Session 1, Chair: John O'Callaghan, CSIRO		
8:50 - 9:00	Opening: John O'Callaghan, CSIRO	Session 5, Chair: Peter Room, CSIRO	Session 9, Chair: Tony Burgess, Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research
9:00 - 9:45	Simulations of biomolecular processes <i>Antony W. Burgess</i> <i>Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research, AUSTRALIA</i>	L-systems: from the theory to plant modeling methodology <i>Przemyslaw Prusinkiewicz</i> <i>University of Calgary, Alberta, CANADA</i>	Protein Dynamics: Correlation between NMR Spectroscopy, X-ray Crystallography and Molecular Dynamics Simulations <i>Carmay Lim</i> <i>Academia Sinica, TAIWAN</i>
9:45 - 10:30	The Visible Human Project - Male and Female <i>Victor Spitzer</i> <i>University of Colorado, Colorado, USA</i>	Practical aspects of virtual plant research <i>Jim Hanan</i> <i>CRC for Tropical Pest Management, Queensland, AUSTRALIA</i>	Molecular Dynamics simulations of membrane proteins <i>Benoit Roux</i> <i>Universite de Montreal, CANADA</i>
10:30 - 11:00	Morning Refreshments	Morning Refreshments	Morning Refreshments
	Session 2, Chair: John B. Furness, University of Melbourne	Session 6, Chair: Jim Hanan, CRC for Tropical Pest Management	Session 10, Chair: Carmay Lim, Academia Sinica, TAIWAN
11:00 - 11:45	Modelling the synapse <i>Max Bennett</i> <i>University of Sydney, NSW, AUSTRALIA</i>	Architectural modelling of trees: A question of detail and complexity <i>W R Remphrey</i> <i>University of Manitoba, Manitoba, CANADA</i>	Reaction mechanisms in enzyme active sites using a "divide and conquer" approach: mixed quantum and molecular mechanics (qm/MM) <i>Jill E. Gready</i> <i>Australian National University, AUSTRALIA</i>
11:45 - 12:30	Action potentials in synaptic boutons and presynaptic inhibition <i>Stephen Redman</i> <i>Australian National University, ACT, AUSTRALIA</i>	Modelling plants in landscapes <i>David Green</i> <i>Charles Sturt University, NSW, AUSTRALIA</i>	Delivering the goods: putting solutions to computational problems into the hands of biologists <i>Tim Littlejohn</i> <i>Australian National Genomic Information Service (ANGIS), AUSTRALIA</i>
12:30 - 14:00	Luncheon	Luncheon	Luncheon
	Session 3, Chair: Max Bennett, University of Sydney	Session 7, Chair: Przemyslaw Prusinkiewicz, University of Calgary	Session 11, Chair: Jill E. Gready, The Australian National University
14:00 - 14:45	Large scale computational reconstruction of enteric nerve circuits <i>Joel Bornstein</i> <i>University of Melbourne, Victoria, AUSTRALIA</i>	Examples of agronomic processes represented with collections of interacting objects <i>Art Diggie</i> <i>University of Western Australia, WA, AUSTRALIA</i>	Protein structure prediction: Meeting the challenge of genome projects <i>Geoffrey J. Barton</i> <i>Laboratory of Molecular Biophysics, University of Oxford, UNITED KINGDOM</i>

14:45 - 15:30	Models of cerebral dynamics <i>James Wright</i> <i>Mental Health Research Institute of Victoria, AUSTRALIA</i>	14:45 - 15:10 Measuring and analysing real plants with the AMAPmod software <i>C. Godin*, Y. Guedon*, E. Costes**, Y. Caraglio*</i> <i>*CIRAD - Centre de cooperation International en Recherche agronomique pour le Developpement, FRANCE</i> <i>**INRA - Institut National de Recherche en Agronomie, FRANCE</i> 15:10 - 15:35 Modelling growth and form of marine sessile suspension feeders <i>Jaap A. Kaandorp & Peter M.A. Sloot</i> <i>University of Amsterdam, THE NETHERLANDS</i>	Graphical representations in sequence analysis <i>Georg F. Weiller</i> <i>Australian National University, ACT, AUSTRALIA</i>
15:30 - 16:00	Afternoon Refreshments	Afternoon Refreshments	Afternoon Refreshments
	Session 4, Chair: Stephen Redman, Australian National University	Session 8, Chair: Richard Silberstein, Swinburne University of Technology	Session 12, Chair: Shoba Ranganathan, The Australian National University
16:00 - 16:20	Large-scale computational simulation of cortex-like systems using a CRAY YMP supercomputer <i>Ben M Ramsden*, Gregory K Egan** and Richard B Silberstein*</i> <i>*Swinburne University of Technology, Victoria, AUSTRALIA</i> <i>**Monash University, Victoria, AUSTRALIA</i>	Computer-aided diagnosis from medical images using anatomical models <i>L.S. Wilson*, M.S. Brown**, S.F. Brown*, V.Vuwong**, B.D. Doust*** and R.W. Gill*</i> <i>*Division of Radiophysics, CSIRO, AUSTRALIA</i> <i>**University of NSW, Sydney, AUSTRALIA</i> <i>***St Vincents Hospital, Sydney, AUSTRALIA</i>	Hybrid system for prediction of MHC class II binding peptides <i>V. Brusic*, G. Rudy*, J. Hammer** and L.C. Harrison*</i> <i>*The Walter and Eliza Hall Institute, Melbourne, AUSTRALIA</i> <i>**Roche Milano Ricerche, Milan, ITALY</i>
16:20 - 16:40	Recent progress in developing computational models of long-term potentiation and depression <i>Christopher Coomber</i> <i>Deakin University, Victoria, AUSTRALIA</i>	POSTER SESSION	16:20 - 16:50 ROUND TABLE: The future of Computational Life Sciences in Australia
16:40 - 17:35	Computation and dynamics in Cognitive Science: An Overview <i>Timothy van Gelder</i> <i>University of Melbourne, Victoria, AUSTRALIA</i>	POSTER SESSION	16:50 - 17:00 Closing
19:00 for 19:30	CONFERENCE DINNER <i>The University House, The University of Melbourne</i>		

Poster session

T.T. Tran, A.W. Burgess, L.C. Groenen and H.R. Treutlein
Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research, P.O. Royal Melbourne Hospital,
Parkville, Vic. 3050, AUSTRALIA
Conformationally specific Amino Acids

Andrew I. Eddy and Dr. Graham A. Bell
CSIRO Division of Food Science and Technology, PO Box 52,
North Ryde, NSW, 2113, AUSTRALIA
Colour video recording of voltage sensitive dyes in animal neural tissue

Peter M. Room and Jim S. Hanan
CSIRO Division of Entomology
and Cooperative Research Centre for Tropical Pest Management,
P.B.No. 3, Indooroopilly, 4068, AUSTRALIA
Virtual Plants: How they are built and used?

John D. Orbell and Elizabeth Yuriev
Dept. of Environmental Management, Victoria University of Technology,
St. Albans, Victoria, AUSTRALIA
Towards quantifying steric effects in metal-complex nucleic acid system

Bohdan Durnota and Sayed Sajeev
Department of Software Development, Monash University,
Caulfield, Victoria, AUSTRALIA
Parallel Simulation of Spatially Explicit Ecosystem Models

ODonohue M.F.*, Burgess A.W.** and Treutlein H.R.**
* Ludwig Institute for Cancer Research, P.O. Royal Melbourne Hospital,
Parkville, Vic. 3050, AUSTRALIA
** CRC for Cellular Growth Factors, P.O. Royal Melbourne Hospital,
Parkville, Vic. 3050, AUSTRALIA
Study of the conformations of wild-type and chemically modified Cyclosporin A

Demonstrations:

Virtual Plants
UniChem
Cerius2
AMAPmod

ABSTRACTS

The Visible Human Project - Male and Female

Victor M. Spitzer

Departments of Cellular and Structural Biology and Radiology
University of Colorado Health Sciences Center
Denver, Colorado, USA

Abstract:

The Visible Human Male was released as a collection of axial cross-sections through the entire body of a 38 year old cadaver. The image database forms a three dimensional volume of human anatomy. Each slice was a digital matrix 1760 x 1024 x 24 bits. There are 1878 images in the database. During the past year we have segmented and classified some regions of the body and in these areas we can render 3D images and begin to interact with the data as will be demonstrated by both surgical simulation and needle insertion simulation with force feedback.

The female was introduced as a similar collection of two dimensional images on November 28, 1995. A major difference between the male and female datasets is the resolution. The female slices are 0.33 mm thick in comparison to the 1 mm thick slices through the male. This provides the same resolution in the xy plane for both cadavers but and allows equivalent resolution in the z axis for the female. (i.e. cubical voxels).

Action potentials in synaptic boutons and presynaptic inhibition

Stephen Redman and Bruce Graham

Division of Neuroscience
John Curtin School of Medical Research
Australian National University
Canberra, ACT
AUSTRALIA

Abstract:

Presynaptic inhibition is mediated by axo-axonic synapses on the synaptic terminals of primary afferent axons. Gamma-amino-butyric acid (GABA) is released at these axo-axonic synapses and binds to both GABAA and GABAB receptors. GABAA receptors mediate an increase in chloride conductance, which depolarizes the nerve terminal and decreases its membrane conductance. GABAB receptor activation decreases the entry of calcium through voltage-gated calcium channels. The contributions of each of these mechanisms to the reduction in release of transmitter from the nerve terminal is unclear. The conventional explanation is that the chloride conductance mediated by GABAA receptors decreases the amplitude of the incoming action potential, thereby reducing calcium influx to the nerve terminal and reducing transmitter release. This process has been modelled.

A propagating action potential was simulated in axons connected to either side of a hemispherical bouton. The axons could be myelinated or unmyelinated, while the bouton membrane could be passive, a node of the myelinated nerve, or have the same active properties as the attached unmyelinated nerve. Membrane properties of the axon were derived from mammalian data. A steady-state chloride conductance was included in the bouton membrane, with $E_{Cl} = -40\text{mV}$. The amplitude of the action potential in the bouton was calculated for different diameters of axon and bouton and for different magnitudes of chloride conductance. Published data was then used to convert the amplitude of the presynaptic action potential into a post-synaptic potential. For realistic geometries, conductance increases in the range 3-10nS were required to alter synaptic transmission. As GABAA mediated conductances with these values are unlikely to occur in terminal membranes, more complicated geometries of terminating axons and boutons and other synaptic mechanisms were investigated in an attempt to reproduce experimental results. These will be presented.

Simulation of the activities of large-scale, anatomically realistic networks of intestinal (enteric) neurons during reflexes

J.C. Bornstein, J.B. Furness, H.F. Kelly, P.P. Bertrand and W.A.A. Kunze

Departments of Physiology and of Anatomy and Cell Biology,
University of Melbourne,
Parkville Vic 3052, Australia

Abstract:

The gastrointestinal tract contains the cell bodies and processes of up to 100,000,000 neurons, the enteric nervous system. These neurons control intrinsic intestinal behaviours including propulsion of contents and movements of water and salts across the intestinal wall. Movements of the intestine underlying propulsion appear to be induced by activation of two anatomically distinct reflex pathways: the ascending excitatory pathway and the descending inhibitory pathway. The elements of these pathways have been identified in physiological and anatomical experiments on confined populations of enteric neurons, but how these elements act together to induce propulsion remains unclear. We have developed a suite of programs to simulate the activities of a large proportion of the enteric neurons during intestinal reflexes with a view to understanding the dynamic relationships between the different types of neurons in the two reflex pathways. The model defined by these programs includes sensory neurons, four types of motor neurons and two types of interneurons, and can be extended by adding extra classes of neurons as needed.

The first program constructs a model circuit containing anatomically realistic numbers of neurons of each functional type. This involves between 10,000 and 100,000 neural elements distributed along the length of intestine to be modelled. The connections between these neurons are set by a second program according to rules laid down by the experimenter and are based on experimentally determined structural and physiological data. Each neuron is assigned its own specified set of input and output connections. The conduction velocities of the neurons are similarly assigned by the program according to rules set by the experimenter. At each point in the process, the network can be stored so that the effects of varying the rules used to assign particular values can be analysed.

Dynamic properties of the individual neurons are simulated using the conductance changes and membrane properties known to be involved in real neural activity. Synaptic events are treated as conductance changes acting upon realistic reversal potentials and are summed to be compared with a preset threshold for generation of action potentials. No attempt is made to realistically simulate the conductance changes underlying action potentials.

The program has been used to simulate reflexes when the output of sensory neurons is via fast or slow excitatory synaptic potentials (EPSPs), as both types of response appear to result from activation of sensory neurons (Kunze et al. 1993, 1995). Neither form of sensory output could, by itself, account for the properties of the ascending reflex pathways. Rather, to achieve a physiologically realistic pattern of activity in interneurons of the ascending pathway, the firing of these neurons during slow EPSPs had to be limited to the beginning of the EPSP. Such limitations have been observed in electrophysiological experiments. However, neurons in the descending

pathway are not limited in this way and simulations of this pathway are now being undertaken.

Kunze WAA, Furness JB & Bornstein JC *Simultaneous intracellular recordings from enteric neurons reveals that myenteric AH neurons transmit via slow excitatory post-synaptic potentials.* Neuroscience **55**:685-694, 1993.

Kunze WAA, Bornstein JC & Furness JB *Physiological identification of sensory nerve cells in a peripheral organ (the intestine) of a mammal.* Neuroscience **66**:1-4, 1995.

Models of cerebral dynamics

James Wright

Mental Health Research Institute of Victoria,
AUSTRALIA

Abstract:

Further results from a simulation which models cerebral cortex (of the cat) as coupled, lumped cell masses, and reproduces spectral and wave-velocity features of the electrocorticogram (ECoG) are presented. Thresholds for action-potential generation in the neuronal population are modelled as Gaussian, with the consequence that coupled cell masses interact with nonlinear gain. However, it is demonstrated that the simulation's wave properties are essentially linear over the relevant range of average pulse density. Nonspecific activation acts to control the system transfer function transforming localised pulse inputs to output ECoG, and partially determines the dominant ECoG rhythm.

When inputs and nonspecific activation to localised cortical areas are modelled the simulation reproduces both the gamma band ECoG activity and the synchronous oscillations of action potentials at zero lag, as reported in physiological experiments.

Computation and dynamics in Cognitive Science: An Overview

Timothy van Gelder

University of Melbourne
Parkville, Victoria, 3052, AUSTRALIA

Abstract:

Cognitive science has traditionally been dominated by the hypothesis that the mind are computers. Increasingly, in recent years, this tradition has been challenged by alternative approaches in which minds are taken to be dynamical systems rather than computers. Yet dynamicists use digital computers in their modeling work, and there is increasing interest in the computational powers of dynamical systems. In this talk I will survey the relevant concepts, and the role of computers and computation in cognitive science. The aim is to be able to articulate a clear version of the dynamical hypothesis as a substantial alternative to the dominant computational hypothesis.

L-systems: from theory to plant modeling methodology

Przemyslaw Prusinkiewicz

Department of Computer Science
The University of Calgary
Calgary, Alberta, Canada

Abstract:

Recent advances in computer graphics have made it possible to visualize mathematical models of biological structures and processes with unprecedented realism. The resulting images, animations, and interactive systems are useful as research and educational tools in developmental biology and ecology. Prospective applications also include computer-assisted landscape architecture, design of new varieties of plants, and crop yield prediction. This presentation will focus on the developmental models of branching plant structures expressed in terms of Lindenmayer systems. After a brief introduction to L-systems and their graphical interpretation, emphasis will be put on constructs that transform L-systems from a theoretical concept to a versatile modeling tool. Selected constructs are listed below.

- (a) Parametric L-systems are particularly suitable for capturing fine details of plant architecture.
- (b) Stochastic L-systems make it possible to take into account the variability between different specimens of the same species; these L-systems are particularly useful when building models according to data obtained by statistical analysis of plant measurements.
- (c) L-system with fragmentation are useful in modeling such effects as plant propagation and shedding of branches.
- (d) Context-sensitive L-systems make it possible to express and simulate involved aspects of plant physiology, such as resource allocation taking place during plant development.
- (e) Environmentally-sensitive L-systems provide a framework for simulating interactions between plants and their environment (for example, interaction between roots and soil, and competition between plants for resources such as nutrients and light)
- (f) Differential L-systems simplify the modeling and visualization of developmental processes when the continuity of the progression of forms is important (for example, in computer animation applications).

The presentation will be illustrated using computer-generated images, animations, and live computer demonstration of some of the models.

Practical aspects of Virtual Plant Research

Jim Hanan

CRC for Tropical Pest Management
CSIRO Division of Entomology
Brisbane, AUSTRALIA

Abstract:

Virtual plants are computer simulations that capture the structural dynamics of plant development, growth, and senescence. They are tools for understanding real plants as individuals made up of components, such as internodes, leaves and flowers, produced by apical meristems. The arrangement of these components in 3D space, the plant's architecture, plays a key role in the gathering of diffuse resources from the environment, and therefore in determining yield and competitive ability. While processes at the level of cellular physiology and of stand biomass have received a lot of attention, relatively little research has been done at this intermediate level due to the difficulty of collecting and analysing the data required. Now, data can be collected using 3-D digitisers and can be analysed and summarized as rules of growth suitable for use in simulation programs. When the simulations are run, the resulting virtual plants can be visualised as schematic or realistic images, giving valuable feedback on the accuracy of the model. Once the modelling process is complete, virtual plants can be used in a number of ways. They can provide a dynamic platform for simulations requiring details of plant architecture, useful in areas such as remote sensing or pesticide application. Virtual experiments can be run to narrow the range of time-consuming real-world experiments required. Virtual plant visualisations will be useful in education and in decision-making by farmers, agronomists and pest managers.

At the Cooperative Research Centre for Tropical Pest Management we are using virtual plants to study how plant-growth patterns are affected by varying locations and amounts of insect damage. This presentation will focus on some practical aspects of using L-system-based virtual plants as a research tool, noting areas where computational challenges exist. Topics covered will include:

- the collection and analysis of plant growth data
- incorporation of physiology from crop models into virtual plants,
- modelling of insect behaviour on a virtual plant, and
- an overview of progress in our modelling of a variety of crop and weed species.

Architectural modelling of trees: A question of detail and complexity

W.R. Remphrey

Department of Plant Science
University of Manitoba
Winnipeg, CANADA

Abstract:

Trees are the largest living organisms. They increase in size by the harmonious integration of complex developmental processes. The result constitutes tree architecture. There are several qualitative tree architecture patterns recognized and several species have also been described quantitatively. The first part of this paper will address the questions: what is quantitative architecture and why should it be quantified?

In the second part, the relationship between quantitative tree architecture and modelling for visualization will be discussed. There are several approaches for modelling tree architecture and these may be described in a matrix defined by level of abstraction and complexity. At a distance, a tree may be represented by colour or textural variation without any perceivable loss of detail. At close range, it is evident that the organism is created by the addition of morphologically similar modules and models must reflect this. Modules may consist of yearly increments of extension growth - shoots, and these form the basis for many simulation models of tree architecture. Shoot modules are a product of the formation of smaller modules - shoot units, consisting of a leaf, bud and stem tissue. The application of levels of abstraction in modelling can be shown in models of *Larix laricina*, a temperate zone conifer. L-systems were used to increase developmental precision by converting a 2-dimensional shoot model into a 3-dimensional model based on shoot units. The cost was an increase in the number of computations necessary.

One way to model complex organisms while still retaining a sufficient level of detail is illustrated in a dynamic L-system approach to modelling *Fraxinus pennsylvanica* crown development over several years. A model is postulated which begins with a detailed real-time model of shoot development, including expansion of leaves. As the tree develops, the model moves up the continuum and becomes more abstract. Leaf detail is reduced and shoot unit iterations are replaced by yearly iterations.

The above models vary in their level of abstraction, but are all based on statistically derived structural information. Regardless of abstraction level, complexity of modelling is increased with the degree of physiological control within the system which increases our understanding of development. Attempts to model at a low level of abstraction and complexity are resulting in computational and conceptual limitations which will be discussed.

Modelling plants in landscapes

David Green

Environmental and Information Science
Charles Sturt University
Albury, NSW 2640, AUSTRALIA

Abstract:

Modelling plant communities is becoming increasingly important in conservation. Typical applications include predicting the geographic distributions of species, simulating community dynamics, and analyzing species viability. In all of the above applications there is increasing awareness of the need to consider interactions - especially between populations, and across landscapes - if models are to yield valid and useful results.

Vector and raster representations of plant distributions both have advantages and drawbacks. Vector models (which represent individual plants) can be especially computationally intensive and difficult to apply to problems on large scale or heterogeneous landscapes. Raster models, in which "pixels" represent areas of the landscape, are less precise but computationally more tractable. They also better reflect major sources of large-scale data, such as satellite imagery.

Interactions within spatial models often lead to completely different dynamics. For instance, models can be locally unstable yet globally persistent. Patchy distributions also affect the behaviour of models. For instance, the behaviour of systems with critical levels of landscape cover is inherently unpredictable. Models of population genetics within a landscape have revealed fresh insights about the mechanics of evolution. The effects of "genetic communication" within a landscape is especially important in considering the viability of small populations.

Examples of agronomic processes represented with collections of interacting objects

Art J. Diggle

Centre for Legumes in Mediterranean Agriculture
University of Western Australia
Perth, WA, AUSTRALIA

Abstract:

Many agronomic processes can be thought of as resulting from the combined action of a large number of mutually similar or identical processes operating at a finer level of resolution. In such cases people often think of the mechanism in terms of the fine level of resolution but wish to estimate the aggregate effect. Modellers have commonly attempted to simulate the aggregate process directly. This approach typically results in models which are as opaque to the user as the system which is being modelled. Such models tend to be computationally efficient, but highly abstract and hence inefficient from a human point of view. The alternative of representing the finer level process as a class, and the aggregate process as a large number of instances of this class produces a much more natural result. A large burden of repetitive calculation is placed on the computer but that of course is the sort of burden for which computers are best suited.

The growth of plant roots is a process which is well suited to this object oriented approach to modelling. Plant root systems are highly complex structures which are extremely difficult to observe directly. However it is clear that root systems are the result of the initiation and growth of a large number of root tips. The probable effects of soil conditions on the growth of individual tips are much more easily conceptualised than the effects on the whole system, yet derivation of the behaviour of the whole system from the combined activities of the tips is quite straight-forward.

Another example is provided by solute movement in soil. Solutes move with the solution, but they exhibit complex three-dimensional dispersion behaviour and typically appear and disappear in a spatially and temporally erratic fashion depending on the activities of plants and other assorted soil organisms. It is difficult to represent this behaviour adequately either by representing the solute concentration in space as a continuous function, or by dividing the volume into regions (such as layers), each with an average solute concentration. By representing the solute as a collection of representative ions each with an exact location however, a conceptually simple and transparent model can be produced.

Breakdown of organic material in soils provides a third example. Soil organic material originates as dead plant material and it is transformed by the action of soil micro-organisms. The resulting material is chemically extremely complex, and it has a wide range of physical associations with large and small mineral particles in the soil. Transformation of soil organic material is usually represented in models by flows between a number of homogeneous pools each with its own static activity and mean composition. An alternative, highly promising approach is to represent additions of soil organic material as individual entities with continually varying properties. This method has the advantage of directly simulating the results of experiments with isotopic labels, and automatically extrapolating results for individual additions to the entire soil. The total number of objects can be kept down to manageable levels by amalgamating additions whose properties have converged to within specified limits.

Protein Dynamics: Correlation between NMR Spectroscopy, X-ray Crystallography and Molecular Dynamics Simulations

Carmay Lim

Academia Sinica
TAIWAN

Abstract:

A ns molecular dynamics simulation of E. Coli RNase HI in the presence of explicit water molecules has been carried out to aid in the interpretation of NMR N-H backbone model free parameters and X-ray B-factor values of the free enzyme. Both experimental techniques have revealed unusual structural and dynamical features of the protein. Atomic fluctuations (B-factors) and re-orientational motions of heteronuclear bonds (order parameters) computed from the simulation are compared with experiment. Reasons for significant discrepancies, the physical basis and the plausible biological consequences of the observed protein dynamics are discussed.

Molecular dynamics studies of lipid-protein interactions

Benoit Roux

Universite de Montreal
CANADA

Abstract:

Lipid-protein interactions are examined at the microscopic level using molecular dynamics simulations of proteins in phospholipid bilayers. The case of the gramicidin A channel, Pf1 phage coat protein, melittin, a poly-leucine helix and PGH S2 are examined. A specially designed construction protocol was used to generate the initial configurations for the simulations of the protein-membrane complex. Analysis of the resulting trajectories shows: a) that the bulk solvent-membrane interface region is much broader than pictured in traditional continuum theories and b) that lipid-protein interactions are far more varied, both structurally and energetically, than is usually assumed in simplified macroscopic theories of lipid-protein interactions. The tryptophans and tyrosine side chains appear to be particularly important in mediating hydrogen bonding interactions with the lipid glycerol backbone and with water while also forming favorable van der Waals contacts with the alkane chains. The results from the simulations are compared with the data obtained from solid state NMR on oriented samples. Continuum electrostatic calculations are used to gain more insight into the thermodynamic stability of membrane proteins.

Protein structure prediction: Meeting the challenge of genome projects

Geoffrey J. Barton

Laboratory of Molecular Biophysics
University of Oxford, U.K.

Abstract:

Over half a million DNA sequences and 100,000 protein sequences have now been determined by experimental methods. With the stimulus of projects to sequence complete genomes and projects to understand inherited diseases, these figures are set to double over the next 18 months. We are at an exciting time for computational biology since experimentalists are generating data too fast for easy analysis by a single group. In traditional sequencing experiments the protein or gene is targeted on the basis of known function. In modern sequencing, the function is often unknown and the challenge to the computational biologist is to predict function from sequence alone. It is the three dimensional structure of the protein that determines its function, but there are currently less than 4,000 structures known to atomic resolution. Accordingly, techniques to predict protein structure from sequence have an important role in aiding our understanding of the Genome and the effects of mutations in genetic disease. At present the most reliable method of predicting the function of a protein is to show sequence similarity to a protein that has already been well characterised. Although there are established techniques to find clear sequence similarities (e.g. dynamic programming) some proteins share similar structures but no sequence similarity. In recent years efforts have concentrated on pushing the limits of detection to include such similarities by the use of environment specific weights or pair potentials. In this lecture I will review some of the recent highlights in this field and discuss a new method for protein fold prediction.

Reaction mechanisms in enzyme active sites using a "divide and conquer" approach: mixed quantum and molecular mechanics (qm/MM)

Jill E. Gready

Computational Molecular Biology and Drug Design Group
Division of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology
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Abstract:

The grand challenge of computational molecular science is to extend the techniques developed over the last 25 years for relatively small molecular systems to the macromolecular systems which are typical in biology. This will allow the relationship between protein structure and function to be studied at a level not possible experimentally. However, because of the size of the systems, the future (foreseeable!) in macromolecular computational chemistry will be in mixed methodologies which treat different parts of the molecular problem with different levels of accuracy, i.e. divide and conquer. The idea of combining quantum mechanical (QM) and molecular mechanical (MM) methods to describe large molecular systems is not new, but its application to systems of real interest has been limited up to now by inadequate computing power. Also, the availability of different QM methods (e.g. *ab initio* or semiempirical) and QM/MM potentials raises some important methodological and practical issues which need to be addressed. These include the form of the potential, the appropriate QM theory for the problem, and the division of the system into QM and MM parts. Some of these developmental issues will be discussed in the context of ongoing work aimed at studying enzymic reaction mechanisms.

To study enzyme catalysis it is necessary to develop an appropriate theoretical model which is both chemically accurate and computationally efficient. This model must be able to describe the chemical bond making and breaking events within the complex active-site environment. Thus it must allow the roles for specific interactions between substrates and cofactors with protein groups, and with solvent mediating such interactions, to be assessed. The problem which will be described is the deceptively simple reaction catalysed by lactate dehydrogenase (LDH). This involves the interconversion of pyruvate to L-lactate in the presence of cofactor nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD), with the transfer of both a proton and hydride ion. The potential energy surface for the LDH enzymic reaction was constructed for proton transfer and hydride transfer reaction coordinates using a QM/MM approach. The results will be compared with an earlier all QM study for a "supermolecule" system consisting of substrate, cofactor and fragments of key active-site groups.

Graphical representations in sequence analysis

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Abstract:

Advances in sequencing technology and genome projects have caused an explosion of readily accessible DNA sequences, and one wonders how biologist can cope with these data. Bioinformatics has set out to turn this biological data into biological information using either fully automated approaches like 'GeneQuiz' and other expert systems or interactive tools that allow the biologist to direct the course of the analysis.

This talk will focus on interactive computer tools that make use of various graphical representations to present information hidden in primary sequence data. Since the human investigator is a better pattern recognisor than any system yet developed we believe that appropriate and intuitive representation of sequence information to the investigator is of crucial value. I will survey several graphical methods of sequence representation and discuss two new methods, 'Distance Plots' and 'Phylogenetic Profiles', that we have developed for visualising evolutionary processes and genetic recombination. The Computer programs 'DiPloMo' and 'PhylPro' which implement these new methods will be presented, and examples involving genes from bacteria and AIDS viruses will be given to demonstrate the far reaching insights that can be achieved with comparable simple graphical methods.

Delivering the goods: putting solutions to computational problems into the hands of biologists

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Abstract:

Many of the challenges in computational biology are related to solving the problems of interpreting, analysing and modelling biological information. The flood of data being generated by modern biology is opening up a number of exciting areas of research: database interoperation, molecular and systems modelling, comparative genomics and proteomics amongst many others.

Computational biology has two goals. Firstly, as a discipline in its own right, bioinformatics has well defined research objectives. Secondly, bioinformatics has a role in putting the results of novel bioinformatics developments into the hands of the biologists where it can be a tool in their research. This latter goal will be the subject of this presentation.

The computational challenges that will be discussed include:

- User interfaces
- Service delivery methods
- Database interoperation
- Software interoperation
- Resource distribution (computational, data, networks)
- Delivering high-performance computing resources
- Documentation & help
- Integration of diverse resources (software, databases, documentation) - "Seamless" resources

These issues will be discussed around the provision of biocomputing resources at a national level, focusing specifically on the resources provided through ANGIS, Australia's National Facility for biocomputing.

Large-scale computational simulation of cortex-like systems using a CRAY YMP supercomputer

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Abstract:

Recently developed imaging techniques such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), brain electrical activity mapping, and optical dye methodology provide neuroscientists with detailed information about the spatio-temporal changes in cortical activity that occur after the presentation of sensory stimuli, or during the performance of behavioural tasks. This information may be used in conjunction with conventional electrophysiological data to delineate significant "nodes" in putative cortical networks, to index cortical dysfunction, and to characterise the interactive processes that occur across long-distance (cortico-cortical) or short-distance (intra-cortical) neuronal connections.

One key issue is how these dynamic patterns of activity may be related to underlying neurophysiological processes and neuroanatomical structures. Researchers have developed a number of large-scale cortical computational simulations that attempt to explore these relationships, but have usually focused on structural features that involve homogeneously-distributed diffuse connectivity only.

A significant feature of neocortical structure is the presence of additional heterogeneously-distributed neuronal connectivity. A substantial proportion of cortico-cortical and intra-cortical connections originate from and terminate within specific layers of the cortex in discrete "patchy" distributions. Such neuronal connections may play an important role in the genesis and distribution of patterns of cortical activity.

Using the CRAY YMP supercomputer, we have implemented a large-scale computational simulation of a cortex-like system that incorporates layer-specific and patchy connectivity. A range of physiological and structural parameters may be specified, including neuromodulatory influences on specific layers and regions. Potential configurations range from dual multi-layered regional arrays of excitatory/inhibitory neuronal aggregates connected by a long-delay pathway (e.g. for a putative cortico-cortical simulation), to many thousands of parallel simulations of disconnected neuronal aggregates (e.g. for a parameter space evaluation).

This simulation software may be used to examine the relationship between structure, function and activity modulation in cortex-like structures. The results of such simulations may in turn be used to

interpret existing experimental data obtained from cortical recordings, or to devise hypotheses regarding cortical activity dynamics for further experimental evaluation.

Recent progress in developing computational models of long-term potentiation and depression

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Abstract:

Several forms of short-term and long-term synaptic modification can be expressed in response to a train of conditioning stimuli. Two such phenomena, long-term potentiation (LTP) and long-term depression (LTD), are receiving intense interest. However, although the molecular mechanisms involved in the induction of these phenomena are generally understood, the events involved in their consolidation and maintenance are still unclear. In this paper, recent progress on two computational models of LTP/LTD will be presented. The first model is a simple phenomenological description of LTP/LTD that is being studied in the context of a compartmental model of a neocortical pyramidal cell. Although quite abstract, the model can reproduce the essential characteristics of homo-synaptic and associative LTP/LTD. The second model, which is still in its infancy, comprises a system of differential equations that have been derived from kinetic equations. This model is based on the assumption that the level of Ca^{2+} /calmodulin is responsible for initiating processes that lead to the induction of both LTP and LTD. Low-levels of this complex trigger LTD, whilst high-levels trigger LTP as a result of competing processes involved in the phosphorylation and dephosphorylation of channel substrates. Both of these models may help the researcher to speculate about the mechanisms controlling LTP/LTD.

Measuring and analysing real plants with the AMAPmod software

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Abstract:

The diversity of plants we investigate has lead us to define a generic methodology for measuring real plants and modeling their growth. This methodology is developed in the AMAPmod software, which provides the user with various tools for encoding, exploring and modeling plants. In a typical experiment, botanical structures of plants are measured in the field, possibly at different level of details. These structures are encoded using a dedicated language in a "coding file". From this description, a formal representation of the plant structures can be built by AMAPmod. This model of the plant structures can represent several plants, both at different scales (using metamer unit and branching system-based unit for example) and at different dates. AMAPmod provides a natural feedback on the measured plants by a realistic 3D graphical reconstruction. The user can then interact with this virtual representation of real plants using the AMAPmod querying language. Three basic types of data can be extracted in the plant according to their structural complexity :

- unstructured data represented by histograms : these data may be modeled by elementary discrete distributions or mixtures of discrete distributions.
- linearly-structured data (or sequence of events) : AMAPmod provides a fully developed set of models based on renewal processes or discrete Markovian processes (Markov chain, non-homogeneous Markov chain, semi-Markov chain, hidden Markov chain, hidden semi-Markov chain).
- tree-structured data : current work is carried out on models able to describe tree-structured data and associated algorithms (e.g. tree matching algorithms are investigated for comparing plant structures).

In AMAPmod, emphasis is put on the learning side of modeling rather than on the simulation side. For all models learning algorithms are available to find optimal set of parameters for samples of data. These models can thus be used as analysis tools in order to reveal levels of organization which cannot be studied efficiently using only direct observations. Current trend is to study how to integrate partial models of plants, at different scales, in a global coherent model.

Modelling growth and form of marine sessile suspension feeders

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Abstract:

The growth form of many marine sessile organisms, as for example sponges, stony-corals, and hydro-corals, is influenced strongly by the physical environment. If the growth process is predominantly heterotrophic and the organism is capturing suspended material from its environment, the growth process is strongly affected by the local availability of suspended material. The distribution of suspended material in a marine environment is determined by a combination of flow and diffusion. The combination of environmental influence and the internal regulation of the growth process, which is in many marine sessile organisms relatively simple compared to for example seed plants and vertebrates, leads to growth forms with a highly complex geometry.

In this paper we will discuss how nutrient distributions, caused by a combination and flow can be modelled with a "particle-based" Lattice Boltzmann method. With this method it is possible to simulate the nutrient distributions in complex geometries in three dimensions and to develop large scale simulations on a parallel machine with distributed memory. >From the nutrient distributions it is possible to model different types of growth processes, which are driven by the local amount of available nutrients. We will discuss two types of nutrient limited growth processes: aggregation models represented in discrete space and accretive growth models where growth is represented in continuous space. Examples of the first type of growth process, diffusion and flow limited aggregation, will be shown on a video.

Computer-aided diagnosis from medical images using anatomical models

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Abstract:

With increasing use of digitally-stored medical images, a role is emerging for computer-aided diagnosis. The role for the computer is as usually as an "expert assistant" or "second opinion" to reduce the risk of missed diagnoses, particularly in screening applications, and commercial systems designed for this purpose are beginning to appear.

While sophisticated pixel-level image processing systems form an important part of such systems, systems based on such processing are limited in their potential applications and are usually unable to capture the higher-level reasoning employed by radiologists who interpret images. Information which comes from different sources (such as different imaging modalities) cannot be directly compared, and anatomical variations (both normal and abnormal) cannot easily be accommodated. We have therefore supplemented pixel-based feature extraction with a powerful, object centred, knowledge-based inferencing system based on anatomical structures and relationships. Most of the knowledge embodied in this scheme is independent of the method used to obtain the image, and relates directly to anatomical knowledge familiar to clinicians.

The anatomical knowledge base also includes organ shape models which may be used for visualisation, atlas matching and manipulation, either in conjunction with the image interpretation software, or for independent applications such as education or surgery planning.

The initial application of the system is an expert assistant for independent, computer-aided diagnosis of chest X-rays to reduce the risk of missed abnormalities. The system has been implemented on a Silicon Graphics Indigo Extreme computer and makes extensive use of frame structures for knowledge management. Inferencing takes place via a blackboard architecture, while the visualisation and modelling are done using Open Inventor.

The preliminary system has proven the usefulness of high-level models in radiological diagnosis, particularly since the knowledge base allows communication with radiologists in familiar terms, and knowledge used by radiologists may be easily incorporated into the system.

Hybrid system for prediction of MHC class II binding peptides

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Abstract:

We have developed a hybrid system for the prediction of peptides that bind to major histocompatibility complex (MHC) molecules. This system utilises experimental binding data and reported binding motifs combined with genetic algorithms (GA) and artificial neural networks (ANN). Binding and non-binding peptides are extracted from the databases and then preprocessed by applying GA to determine potential alignments of the peptides. Known binding motifs are used to fix alignments relative to primary anchor positions. The highest scoring alignments are then selected to train a standard back-propagation ANN to classify peptides by their binding affinity.

We have tested the ability of the hybrid system to predict peptides that bind the human class II MHC molecule HLA-DRB1*0401. The data set included 337 binders and 313 non-binders. The training set and the test set were 2/3 and 1/3 of the data set respectively. Overall sensitivity was 75% and specificity 82% with respective positive and negative predictive values 68% and 84%. High affinity binders were predicted with a positive predictive value of 84%. The system can be optimised for either high sensitivity or high specificity.

Conformationally specific Amino Acids

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Abstract:

Protein engineering using the standard 20 genetically coded amino acids is restricted by the limited repertoire of residues. Although remarkable structural and functional diversity can be generated by variations in polypeptide primary sequences, the incorporation of non-standard amino acids with well-defined stereo-chemical functional properties would greatly enhance the scope of protein engineering. This project aims at extending the repertoire of residues beyond the 20 genetically coded amino acids, i.e. investigating the possibility of designing synthetic amino acids that will restrict the conformations available to a particular residue in a protein.

The conformational properties of thioamide linked peptides have not been explored in detail. It is thought that the bulkiness of the sulphur atom could restrict the conformational spaces that are energetically favourable.

As a prerequisite to the exploration of the thioamide linked peptide, parameters for the thioamide group have been developed for the molecular mechanics CFF91 force field. Ab initio quantum chemical codes such as Gaussian give an accurate approximation of the potential energy surface. However, it is too slow for calculations of proteins. In order to increase the speed of the calculations, the potential energy surface of a molecule is approximated by an empirical molecular force field. A set of force field parameters for the thio group was obtained by least square fit between the Ab Initio calculated and the force field calculated energies, first derivatives and second derivatives. The parameters have been refined by fitting to experimentally obtained crystal and vibrational frequency data.

Using the newly derived force field, ((,() maps of N-Acetyl-Ni-Methyl-Thio-Alanine show more restricted conformation as compared to the N-Acetyl-NiMethyl-Alanine. The restriction mainly focus around (=60(30° where the sulphur atom is eclipsed with the C(Methyl group. N-Acetyl-Ni-Methyl-Thio-Alanine was synthesized and crystallized. The X-ray diffraction structure was solved and its (and (dihedral angles were consistent with the predicted values. Further effects of this thio substitution in (-helices and (-sheets are currently being examined.

Colour video recording of voltage sensitive dyes in animal neural tissue

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Abstract:

Voltage Sensitive Dyes (VSD) have been used for several years to visualise electrical activity in animal neural tissues. VSD's bind to the inside of a cell membrane and respond to a transmembrane electrical potential by changing conformation. This conformation change results in a change in the fluorescence emission spectrum of the dye under a visible light epifluorescence microscope. Experimenters currently using VSD techniques use NTSC monochrome video cameras or purpose-built diode arrays, both of which detect the spectral shift as a small drop in luminance. This method is sensitive to small changes in incident light levels and differences in dye loading across the tissue sample. A PAL-D colour video camera senses the spectral shift as a shift in the relative response of the green- and red-sensitive CCD's. This colour shift, when calculated as a shift in hue angle, is independent of incident light intensity and the amount of loaded dye, and directly related to changes in transmembrane potential. The amount of data contained in a PAL-D colour video signal is about three times that contained in an NTSC monochrome video signal. The analogue-to-digital conversion and storage of this data, and its calculation and display as a hue shift, requires proportionally more computer storage and processing capacity. The Silicon Graphics Indy workstation has standard built-in colour video image capture, enough processing capacity, and the software tools to develop an easy-to-use GUI-based image capture and analysis software suite. We have successfully implemented colour video image capture and analysis of VSD's at a higher sensitivity and a greater freedom from artifacts than current monochrome recording methods.

Virtual Plants: How they are built and used?

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Abstract:

This poster illustrates the processes of making 3-D measurements of growth by real plants, derivation of rules for structural growth, interpretation of the rules to generate virtual plants (simulations of the structural dynamics of individual plants in 3-D space), and use of virtual plants to explore interesting questions. The use of 3-D digitisers is described, including new software which guides an operator to obtain cartesian coordinates for predefined points in the correct sequence. Other software converts the coordinates into angles, lengths and orientations which are processed using standard database and spreadsheet programs to calculate rates of extension etc. from successive measurements of the same plant parts. Rules of development and growth derived from the resulting statistics are expressed as L-system productions. The L-systems are interpreted by the plant and fractal generator program to create virtual plants. The virtual laboratory in botany provides tools for manipulation of model parameters so that 'what if?' questions can be explored by simulation. Work is underway to allow existing models of plant physiology to control rates of growth, biomass partitioning etc. in virtual plants and to allow simulation of interactions between plant growth and attack by insects and diseases.

Towards quantifying steric effects in metal-complex nucleic acid system

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Abstract:

The binding of metal species to nucleic acids is expected to affect a wide range of biological outcomes. More specifically, by binding to DNA, some metal species such as the now familiar cisplatin (cis-dichlorodiammineplatinum (II)) show dramatic cytotoxic and antineoplastic activity. Attempts to describe the steric aspects of these interactions have been primarily qualitative in nature. For inorganic systems up until recently there has been a paucity of appropriate quantitative steric descriptors which may be applied with confidence to investigations such as QSAR. In this work for the approach of metal complexes to a variety of binding sites on nucleobases a repulsive energy strategy is employed in an attempt to delineate relative steric contributions in a quantitative way. Two methods are implemented: (a) Ligand Repulsive Energy (LRE) expressed by the gradient of the van der Waals repulsive energy between the ligand (nucleobase) and a "steric probe" to which it is bound; (b) Complex Repulsive Energy (CRE) expressed by the gradient of the van der Waals repulsive energy between the metal-carrier ligand moiety and a nucleobase of interest to which it is bound. The first parameter is more descriptive of steric factors influencing the approach. The second parameter is also representative of steric factors after the formation of the final adduct.

Parallel simulation of spatially explicit Ecosystem Models

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Abstract:

Spatially explicit models of ecosystems of more and more complexity are currently being developed. Not only may there be a large number of spatial elements (patches), but each patch may itself be subject to a number of complicated processes. For example, in a model currently under development, the patch dynamics includes multiple, interacting stage-structured populations, speciation and extinction events, dispersal across patches, and other factors. The inevitable computationally intensive nature of such models necessitates looking at distributed computational solutions at implementing such models. In this paper we look at a number current parallel spatial ecological modelling systems and compare their functionalities with respect to programming in the principal paradigms of parallelism: result parallelism, specialist parallelism and agenda parallelism. These systems include Tempest, BSIM, MEERC's distributed spatial modelling environment, and DEVS. We also compare these approaches to an attempt by us to use the Linda coordination language.

Study of the conformations of wild-type and chemically modified Cyclosporin A

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Abstract:

Cyclosporin A, a cyclic peptide of eleven residues, is found in a variety of backbone conformations. The effect on conformation of chemical modification of residue side chains as well as that of environmental factors such as temperature and solvent polarity has long been of interest. We have performed molecular dynamics simulations of cyclosporin A and a number of cyclosporin analogues under a variety of conditions. During all simulations the structural transitions of backbone conformations were monitored and populations of each conformation were determined. Here we present a detailed analysis of backbone conformational changes that occur within each environment. The differences between each environment will be discussed. We have developed a new technique and computer program for the efficient analysis and visualisation of conformational changes which occur during a molecular dynamics simulation. The technique defines a conformational state as a collection of values from individual selection criteria. The selection criteria chosen is at the discretion of the user, and can include regions of a phi-psi map, ranges of values for dihedral angles, or individual angle ranges. The computer program incorporates a variety of analysis and display features. The technique has been used in the analysis of the cyclosporin A, but is applicable for conformational analysis of peptides in general.

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University House
Conference dimer

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(1.5km)

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TO CENTRAL
MELBOURNE
(1.5km)

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Women's
Hospital

MUSEUM
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